

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF MARKETING IN MANAGING HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. This article explores the scientific and theoretical foundations of organizing marketing in higher educational institutions. It emphasizes ways to effectively apply marketing principles in managing educational organizations. The paper examines the role of marketing in the modern education system, the key tasks and distinctive features of educational marketing in enhancing competitiveness, and the characteristics of utilizing educational services under current conditions.

Keywords: *educational marketing, segmentation, customer, market, price, supply, demand, marketing strategy, integration, internal and external environment, strategic analysis.*

Introduction. The role of marketing in the current modern education system, its main tasks and specific features in enhancing the competitiveness of higher education, and the characteristics of applying educational services under current conditions are of great importance. In the context of globalization of the education system, the intensification of competition in the educational services market, and the tightening of requirements for educational institutions, it becomes necessary to change the fundamental paradigm of behavior of educational entities and transition to a new active marketing position.

The *Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030* also emphasizes the reform of the higher education system based on modern requirements. This document sets the strategic goal of "increasing the level of coverage of higher education, training highly qualified, creative and systematic thinking personnel, capable of making independent decisions based on international standards, creating the necessary conditions for their intellectual abilities to be demonstrated and their formation as

spiritually mature individuals."

All of the above documents, aimed at further developing and improving the educational process based on modern requirements share common aspects related to introducing innovations into the education and upbringing system, educating youth who think creatively, assimilating foreign experiences, supporting creative approaches, and strengthening integration processes between types of education.

Main part.

The role of marketing in the modern education system is highly relevant, as institutions need to develop effective marketing strategies to succeed in a competitive education market.

To withstand healthy competition among educational institutions, it is first necessary to develop a comprehensive understanding of the characteristics of an institution's marketing activities. This includes:

- developing skills to analyze the situation in the educational services market:
- making decisions based on the state of the marketing environment surrounding the educational institution:
- formulating and implementing marketing strategies for promoting the institution:
- creating and strategically promoting the institution's brand:
- develop the ability to promote educational services in the market.

To build these competences, it is essential to develop a marketing concepts which includes the stages:

- conducting a strategic analysis of the internal and external environment;
- determining the goals of marketing activities and the institution;
- determining the marketing strategy;
- selecting elements of marketing activities to achieve the planned results.

Currently, while public and private educational institutions are fiercely

competing in the market, many institutions are losing their market position due to a lack of marketing knowledge and inability to apply it effectively. As a result, investments made in education are failing to yield returns.

Modern marketing plays an important role in expanding the reach of learners in the market. To understand marketing in educational institutions, one must first grasp its essence.

Marketing is the process of studying the market and presenting a product or service to the customer. Its core concepts include:

Market – the place where supply and demand for a product or service meet, and goods are exchanged between buyers and sellers.

Demand - the quantity and price at which consumers are willing to purchase a product or service.

Supply – the quantity and price at which producers are willing to sell a product or service.

Price - the amount a customer pays for a product or service. It is a key factor in marketing and significantly influences purchasing decisions.

Promotion – Activities aimed at informing customers about a product or service and increasing demand, including advertising, discounts, and campaigns.

Distribution - the process of delivering a product or service to customers through channels such as retail stores and online platforms.

The customer - the central focus of marketing. Products and services are designed to meet their needs.

Market segmentation - dividing a market into different segments, each with its own unique needs and characteristics.

By understanding and applying these concepts, educational institutions will gain the following competencies:

1. Understand and analyze the basic concepts of a market economy and the laws and principles of organizing the marketing activities in educational institutions.
2. Distinguish the specific features, parameters, and classifications of educational services.
3. Know how to apply the basic principles of marketing tactics and strategy in educational organizations.
4. Master core concepts of marketing such as "demand and supply", "market types", "prices and its formation", "product quality", "economic conditions and competitiveness".
5. Respond flexibly to changing market conditions and propose management decision options.
6. Independently segment specific markets for educational services.
7. Possess organizational methods for conducting marketing research and understand the structure of a university's marketing department.
8. Identify the necessary technical tools and methodological approaches for managing marketing in educational organizations.

Summary

Activities related to developing, researching, and managing educational marketing strategies for successfully delivering personnel or services to the market strengthen the position of educational institutions. In the field of marketing, it is important to define institutional goals, study market segments, analyze consumer needs, and monitor competitors. This helps in selecting appropriate marketing tools, positioning the brand, developing pricing policies, and creating effective advertising strategies. Proper marketing management also leads to long-term relationships with customers and increases institutional revenue.

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